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Analogies between Density Functional Theory Response Kernels and Derivatives of Thermodynamic State Functions

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Abstract: In view of its use as reactivity theory, Conceptual Density Functional Theory (DFT), introduced by Parr *et al.*, has mainly concentrated up to now on the $E = E[N, v]$ functional. However, different ensemble representations can be used involving other variables also, such as ρ and μ . In this study, these different ensemble representations (E , Ω , F , and R) are briefly reviewed. Particular attention is then given to the corresponding second-order (functional) derivatives, and their analogies with the second-order derivatives of thermodynamic state functions U , F , H , and G , which are related to each other *via* Legendre transformations, just as the DFT functionals (Nalewajski and Parr, 1982). Starting from an analysis of the convexity/concavity of the DFT functionals, for which explicit proofs are discussed for some cases, the positive/negative definiteness of the associated kernels is derived and a detailed comparison is made with the thermodynamic derivatives. The stability conditions in thermodynamics are similar in structure to the convexity/concavity conditions for the DFT functionals. Thus, the DFT functionals are scrutinized based on the convexity/concavity of their two variables, to yield the possibility of establishing a relationship between the three second-order reactivity descriptors derived from the considered functional. Considering two ensemble representations, F and Ω , F is eliminated as it has two dependent (extensive) variables, N and ρ . For Ω , on the other hand, which is concave for both of its intensive variables (μ and v), an inequality is derived from its three second-order (functional) derivatives: the global softness, the local softness, and the softness kernel. Combined with the negative value of the diagonal element of the linear response function, this inequality is shown to be compatible with the Berkowitz-Parr relationship, which relates the functional derivatives of ρ with v , at constant N and μ . This was recently at stake upon quantifying Kohn's Nearsightedness of Electronic Matter. The analogy of the resulting inequality and the thermodynamic inequality for the G derivatives is highlighted. Potential research paths for this study are briefly addressed; the analogies between finite-temperature DFT response functions and their thermodynamic counterparts and the quest for analogous relationships, as derived in this paper, for DFT functionals that are analogues of entropy-dimensioned thermodynamic functions such as the Massieu function.

Key Words: Conceptual DFT; Response kernels; Analogy with thermodynamics; Stability-concavity/convexity

1 Introduction

Within the context of Conceptual Density Functional Theory (CDFT, sometimes also referred to as chemical reactivity DFT)^{1–7}, the quantification of various previously well known chemical concepts, which lacked a strong formal basis, has become possible. This is done through so-called response

functions of the energy functional $E[N, v]$ where N is the number of electrons of the system and v is the external potential acting on the electrons. Since chemical reactions can be thought of as perturbations in the number of electrons and/or the external potential of a system, it should in theory be possible to study the reactivity of a system through the

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investigation of the response of its energy. Rather than studying the response of the energy in its entirety, we can look at the functional Taylor expansion of the energy and identify the (mixed) functional derivatives of E with respect to N and $v(\mathbf{r})$, ($\delta^{n+m}E/\partial N^n \delta v^m$), as response functions or reactivity indices. The two first order derivatives, the electronic density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ and the electronic chemical potential μ , have been studied intensively as well as two of the second order derivatives, the chemical hardness and the Fukui function $f(\mathbf{r})$ ³.

The third one, the linear response kernel, $\chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$, is well known in theoretical physics and in the chemical physics literature, however essentially in its frequency dependent form $\chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \omega)$. In time dependent DFT⁸ its use is ubiquitous as its poles correspond to the system's excitation energies⁹. Until recently its frequency independent or static analogue, though initiated already for example in Parr and Yang's book¹⁰, received little attention as compared to other conceptual DFT based reactivity descriptors. Recent studies by the present authors provided computational and interpretational strategies for its study and revealed the rich chemical information hidden in this six-variable kernel¹¹⁻²¹, up to its connection with the conductance properties of molecular electronic devices²².

It is well known that different ensemble representations can be used in density-functional theory. The most common, based on the $E[N, v]$ functional, is the so called canonical ensemble of the total energy E as a function of the total number of electrons, N , and the external potential, v :

$$E = E[N, v] \quad (1)$$

Legendre transformations can be used to find other ensemble representations for the ground state²³. This yields the grand canonical, isomorphic and grand isomorphic ensembles, for which the respective Legendre transformations are:

$$\Omega[\mu, v] \equiv E - \mu N \quad (2)$$

$$F[N, \rho] \equiv E - \int \rho(\mathbf{r})v(\mathbf{r})d\mathbf{r} \quad (3)$$

$$R[\mu, \rho] \equiv E - \mu N - \int \rho(\mathbf{r})v(\mathbf{r})d\mathbf{r} \quad (4)$$

In each of these representations a non-local second order derivative or kernel can be defined, namely the linear response function (for E), the softness kernel (for Ω) and the hardness kernel (for F).

Looking at the literature some kernels received more attention than others. As stated above, the linear response kernel, although already discussed by Parr and Berkowitz²⁴ in the late eighties remained somewhat unexplored except in more formal works mainly by Senet, Ayers and Liu²⁵⁻²⁸ until the recent studies mentioned above. The softness kernel was introduced by Berkowitz and Parr²⁴ and its relationship with the local softness $s(\mathbf{r})$ proposed by Yang and Parr²⁹ was discussed. This integrated form of the softness kernel gained widespread use in the literature, e.g. in applying the HSAB

principle at local level³⁰⁻³². Though, the kernel's properties, and its *ab initio* evaluation have been discussed only rarely, an example being some recent work on its *ab initio* evaluation by some of the present authors³³ and its role in the quantitative testing, at molecular level, of Kohn's nearsightedness of electronic matter principle³⁴⁻³⁶. The hardness kernel on the other hand received much more attention often in view of the non-univocal definition of its local counterpart, the local hardness, at first sight the natural companion of the local softness²⁴. A complete bibliography on this issue is beyond the scope of this paper, but for early work we refer to Ghosh *et al.*³⁷⁻³⁹, Harbola⁴⁰, Langenaeker, Torrent-Sucarrat and some of the present authors⁴¹⁻⁴³; for an intermediate status report to Chattaraj's 2003 critical account⁴⁴ and for very recent work to Polanco-Ramirez, containing references to the very recent literature⁴⁵. The R kernel received very little attention except in the study by Liu and Parr⁴⁶, the reason becoming obvious later on in this paper.

The large majority of these studies on the kernels mentioned above, as natural in the context of conceptual or chemical reactivity DFT, concentrated on the role of the kernels on describing chemical reactivity. In the present paper a different aspect of these kernels is highlighted based on the analogy of these functionals with thermodynamic state functions and their properties. The apparent parallelism between classical thermodynamics and DFT has already been addressed in the eighties by Nalewajski and Parr by reformulating the basic variational problem of DFT in terms of various Legendre transformed representations²³.

In the present paper which is partly of a perspective-type we thought to be interesting for this Special Issue, we elaborate further on these analogies starting from the convexity/concavity properties of the DFT functionals with respect to ρ and v , where the $E = E(v)$ case goes back to Lieb⁴⁷, Eschrig⁴⁸, with recent work by Helgaker *et al.*⁴⁹ and our group²¹ connecting it with the properties of the associated kernels (Note that the convexity of the $E = E(N)$ functional and its piecewise linearity have already been deeply analysed in the seminal contribution by Perdew, Parr, Levy and Balduz⁵⁰. A companion paper⁵¹ will be devoted to the more purely mathematical properties of the kernels. Note that we will not concentrate on thermodynamic transcriptions of DFT leading to local thermodynamics (see Ghosh, Parr, Nagy *et al.*⁵²⁻⁵⁵, ...) but that we stick to the original functionals of DFT (E and its Legendre transforms-*vide infra*).

We first restate the formal analogy between the different DFT functionals and the thermodynamic functions, analyzing the type and combinations of variables, using the Legendre transform approach (Section 2.1). In Section 2.2 we consider the positive and negative semidefiniteness of the kernels starting from the convexity/concavity property of the

functionals. In Section 2.3 we concentrate on the analogies between the stability analysis of thermodynamic functions⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ and the convexity/concavity analysis of the DFT functionals and the repercussions on the relationship between thermodynamical derivatives and DFT reactivity descriptors, placing the Berkowitz Parr relationship in a broader context and highlighting in the Grand Canonical Ensemble an inequality involving global softness, local softness and the softness kernel which can be seen as an analogue between a thermodynamic inequality involving the Gibbs free energy derivatives.

2 Results and discussion

2.1 The different ensemble representations and the analogy with thermodynamics: thermodynamic potentials and DFT functionals

Starting from the canonical ensemble of the total energy E as a function of the total number of electrons, N , and the external potential, v ,

$$E = E[N, v], \quad (5)$$

Legendre transformations can be used to find other ensemble representations for the ground state, namely the grand canonical, isomorphic and grand isomorphic ensembles, with the defining equation (see for example reference⁵⁶)

$$\mathcal{L}(f(x, y)) = f - wy = g(x, w) \text{ with } w = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right)_x \quad (6)$$

$$\Omega[\mu, v] \equiv E - \mu N \quad (7)$$

$$F[N, \rho] \equiv E - \int \rho(\mathbf{r})v(\mathbf{r})d\mathbf{r} \quad (8)$$

$$R[\mu, \rho] \equiv E - \mu N - \int \rho(\mathbf{r})v(\mathbf{r})d\mathbf{r} \quad (9)$$

The Legendre transformation connects two ways of specifying the same physics, *via* functions of two related (“conjugate”) variables. In this case the conjugate pairs of variables are the number of electrons N and the chemical potential μ , on one hand and the external potential $v(\mathbf{r})$ and the electron density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ on the other hand. The analogy with classical thermodynamics is apparent, where, at constant particle number, the Legendre transformations are used to convert between the internal energy U (as a function of the entropy S and the volume V), Helmholtz free energy F , enthalpy H , and Gibbs free energy G state functions of the system:

$$U = U(S, V) \quad (10)$$

$$F(T, V) = U - TS \quad (11)$$

$$H(S, p) = U + pV \quad (12)$$

$$G(T, p) = U - TS + pV \quad (13)$$

Here, the two conjugate pairs of variables are pressure p and volume V on one hand, and temperature T and entropy S on the other hand. S and V are so-called extensive variables,

while p and T are intensive. One of the state functions (U) thus depends on two extensive variables, two (F and H) depend on both an intensive and extensive variable and one (G) depends on two intensive variables. The Legendre transformations, as written above, can be seen as the gradual replacement of extensive variables by intensive ones. Please note that all of the above mentioned thermodynamic functions are also depending on the number of particles N ; as however its dependence is not considered explicitly in the remaining text (N is kept constant) we will not denote it explicitly in order to simplify the notation. Nalewajski and Parr²³ extended the notion of “extensive” variables to the microscopic world as “properties additive with respect to any partitioning of the electronic density $\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \rho_A(\mathbf{r}) + \rho_B(\mathbf{r})$ ”. $v(\mathbf{r})$ and μ are clearly not additive with respect to such partitioning of the density and are intensive as opposed to $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ and N which are clearly extensive, the former by definition, the latter as can be seen by integrating the defining equation of $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ to $N = N_A + N_B$. These observations will be of importance when discussing concavity and convexity of the functionals and their repercussion on the response functions. Note that in DFT besides intensive and extensive variables one also distinguishes between global and local quantities^{1,3} varying from point to point (local) or not (global); global and local softness (S and $s(\mathbf{r})$) are typical examples (*vide infra*). In the variables mentioned above there is no one-to-one correspondence between intensive/extensive character on one hand and local/global on the other hand. N for example is extensive and global, ρ is extensive but local.

In the context of density functional theory, the appearance of the four Legendre transformations is thus analogous to the thermodynamics case, be it, (1) that one works with functionals instead of functions, (2) that one now “starts” from a functional, E , with one intensive and one extensive variable (v and N) instead of $U(S, V)$ containing two extensive variables and (3) that the third functional, F being nothing else than the Hohenberg-Kohn functional, actually only depends on the density, $\rho(\mathbf{r})$: the expected dependency on N drops since $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ obviously also determines N . It would be interesting to investigate in more detail if there is not an inherent difficulty in using the Legendre Transform procedure at zero temperature, (see⁵⁹, footnote 85). Note that also in this case two functionals (E and R) are dependent on one extensive and one intensive variable/function (as in the thermodynamic case) and one is dependent on two intensive variables (Ω), in analogy with G in thermodynamics.

2.2 Convexity/concavity of the functionals and positive/negative semidefiniteness of the kernels

Each different functional, corresponding to a different representation, gives rise to one non-local second order response function, a kernel, in v or ρ . Explicitly written, they

are

$$\left(\frac{\delta^2 E}{\delta v(\mathbf{r})\delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_N = \left(\frac{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_N = \chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \quad (14)$$

$$\left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta v(\mathbf{r})\delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu = \left(\frac{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu = -s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \quad (15)$$

$$\left(\frac{\delta^2 F}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right) = \frac{\delta}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')} (\mu - v(\mathbf{r})) = \eta(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \quad (16)$$

$$\left(\frac{\delta^2 R}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu = -\left(\frac{\delta v(\mathbf{r})}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu = t(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \quad (17)$$

where we recognise the linear response function $\chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$, the softness and hardness kernels $s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ and $\eta(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ whereas the final kernel $t(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ has not been given a particular name, for reasons that will become obvious later. All kernels are symmetric in \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{r}' . Note that in the hardness kernel no constraints are imposed when performing the functional differentiation in view of the absence of the expected explicit N dependence discussed before. Note also the $-$ sign in front of $s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$. The analogy between $\chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ and $s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is striking: they both involve the functional derivative of $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ with respect to $v(\mathbf{r}')$, however with a different constraint: constant N for χ and constant μ for s . The importance of this difference has already been stressed in early work by Berkowitz and Parr²⁴, its repercussions when quantifying Kohn's nearsightedness of electronic matter principle^{34,35} have been at stake in recent work by some of the present authors³⁶.

We now investigate the positive or negative semidefiniteness of the kernels, as resulting from the convexity/concavity of the functionals.

Using a functional Taylor series of the electronic energy E for which the initial (or unperturbed) external potential $v(\mathbf{r})$ is perturbed by $w(\mathbf{r})$, the next expression, up to second order is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} E[v(\mathbf{r}) + w(\mathbf{r})] = & \\ E[v(\mathbf{r})] + \int \left(\frac{\delta E}{\delta v(\mathbf{r})}\right)_N w(\mathbf{r})d\mathbf{r} + & \\ \frac{1}{2} \iint \left(\frac{\delta^2 E}{\delta v(\mathbf{r})\delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_N w(\mathbf{r})w(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}' & \quad (18) \end{aligned}$$

It is well established that $E[v]$ functional is concave, following Jensen's inequality (see for example Lieb⁴⁷, Eschrig⁴⁸, Helgaker *et al.*⁴⁹):

$$\begin{aligned} E[\lambda v_1(\mathbf{r}) + (1-\lambda)v_2(\mathbf{r})] \geq & \\ \lambda E[v_1(\mathbf{r})] + (1-\lambda)E[v_2(\mathbf{r})] \quad \forall \lambda \in [0, 1] & \quad (19) \end{aligned}$$

This concavity implies the linear response to be negative semidefinite:

$$\iint \chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')\theta(\mathbf{r})\theta(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}' \leq 0 \quad (20)$$

for any continuous function θ . This can be seen from:

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{E[v + \epsilon w] + E[v - \epsilon w] - 2E[v]}{\epsilon^2} \right] =$$

$$\iint \chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')w(\mathbf{r})w(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}' \quad (21)$$

and by recognizing that 19 implies that

$$\begin{aligned} E\left[\frac{1}{2}(v + \epsilon w) + \frac{1}{2}(v - \epsilon w)\right] & \geq \frac{1}{2}E[v + \epsilon w] + \frac{1}{2}E[v - \epsilon w] \\ 2E[v] & \geq E[v + \epsilon w] + E[v - \epsilon w] \\ 0 & \geq E[v + \epsilon w] + E[v - \epsilon w] - 2E[v] \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Passing now to the grand canonical ensemble, similar to the convexity of the $E[v]$ functional, it can be shown that $\Omega[v] = E[v] - \mu N$ is concave (for a complete proof, see⁵¹):

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega[\lambda v_1(\mathbf{r}) + (1-\lambda)v_2(\mathbf{r})] \geq & \\ \lambda\Omega[v_1(\mathbf{r})] + (1-\lambda)\Omega[v_2(\mathbf{r})] \quad \forall \lambda \in [0, 1], & \quad (23) \end{aligned}$$

From this concavity it follows again that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\Omega[v + \epsilon w] + \Omega[v - \epsilon w] - 2\Omega[v]}{\epsilon^2} \right] = & \\ - \iint s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')w(\mathbf{r})w(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}' \leq 0, & \quad (24) \end{aligned}$$

implying that the softness kernel $s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is positive semidefinite. This positive semidefiniteness is also evident when using the Berkowitz-Parr relation for $s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$:

$$\begin{aligned} \iint s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')\theta(\mathbf{r})\theta(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}' = & \\ \iint \left[-\chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') + \frac{f(\mathbf{r})f(\mathbf{r}')}{\eta} \right] \theta(\mathbf{r})\theta(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}' = & \\ - \iint \chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')\theta(\mathbf{r})\theta(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}' + & \\ \frac{1}{\eta} \left[\int f(\mathbf{r})\theta(\mathbf{r})d\mathbf{r} \right]^2 \geq 0, & \quad (25) \end{aligned}$$

since the hardness, η is positive.

In the isomorphic ensemble we remind that the Hohenberg-Kohn functional, F , actually only depends on the density, $\rho(\mathbf{r})$, since this obviously also determines N . Keeping, however, the spirit of the Legendre transformation of $E[N, v(\mathbf{r})]$ to $F[N, \rho(\mathbf{r})]$ in mind, it is tempting to look at variations in ρ while fixing the number of electrons.

$$\left(\frac{\delta^2 F}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_N = -\left(\frac{\delta v(\mathbf{r})}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_N = q(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \quad (26)$$

This kernel $q(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$, which can be viewed as a special case of the hardness kernel under constant N variations of ρ , and has the interesting corollary of being the inverse of the linear response kernel:

$$\begin{aligned} \int \chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')q(\mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}'')d\mathbf{r}' = & \\ - \int \left(\frac{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_N \left(\frac{\delta v(\mathbf{r}')}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}'')}\right)_N d\mathbf{r}' = -\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'') & \quad (27) \end{aligned}$$

In what follows, we will restrict however our discussion to the "classical" hardness kernel, defined in Eq. (17) without constraint. We now consider the convexity of $F[\rho(\mathbf{r})]$ concentrating on the case of v -representable densities, at stake in the type of studies in conceptual DFT (for a more detailed discussion, see Eschrig⁴⁸, Lieb⁴⁷, Ayers⁶⁰). Its convexity

follows from the variational principle. Indeed, if ρ_0 and ρ_1 are pure state v -representable densities and if we suppose that the convex sum $\rho_\lambda = \lambda\rho_0 + (1-\lambda)\rho_1$ also belongs to the domain of pure state v -representable densities, then due to the variational principle $F[\rho_\lambda] \leq \lambda F[\rho_0] + (1-\lambda)F[\rho_1]$, or in other words F is a convex functional (see ⁵¹ for more details).

From this convexity it follows that

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{F[\rho + \epsilon w] + F[\rho - \epsilon w] - 2F[\rho]}{\epsilon^2} \right] = \iint \eta(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') w(\mathbf{r}) w(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \geq 0, \quad (28)$$

implying that the hardness kernel $\eta(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is positive semidefinite.

Finally, we consider the grand isomorphic ensemble. Discussions/use of this functional are less prominent in the literature despite the analysis made already in literature ⁴⁶ by Parr and Liu. As its convexity/concavity in ρ has not been discussed explicitly at that place we show below that R is convex in ρ .

Indeed $R(\rho)$ can be written for a given μ as

$$R_\mu[\rho] = F[\rho] - \mu N[\rho] \quad (29)$$

Suppose we define, just as in the F case, the density

$$\rho_\lambda = \lambda\rho_0 + (1-\lambda)\rho_1 \quad (30)$$

If we define

$$N_0 = \int \rho_0 d\mathbf{r} \quad \text{and} \quad N_1 = \int \rho_1 d\mathbf{r} \quad (31)$$

we now prove that

$$N[\lambda\rho_0 + (1-\lambda)\rho_1] = \lambda N_0 + (1-\lambda)N_1 \quad (32)$$

Indeed

$$\begin{aligned} N[\lambda\rho_0 + (1-\lambda)\rho_1] &= \int (\lambda\rho_0 + (1-\lambda)\rho_1) d\mathbf{r} = \\ &= \lambda \int \rho_0 d\mathbf{r} + (1-\lambda) \int \rho_1 d\mathbf{r} = \\ &= \lambda N_0 + (1-\lambda)N_1 \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

As $F[\rho]$ was convex, this result yields a convex $R[\rho]$. On this basis the corresponding functional derivative $\left(\frac{\delta^2 R}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu$ is positive semidefinite.

$$\begin{aligned} \iint \left(\frac{\delta^2 R}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu \theta(\mathbf{r})\theta(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' &= \\ \iint t(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \theta(\mathbf{r})\theta(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

In fact this could be expected by the mere fact that $t(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ turns out to be equal to the hardness kernel (cf. reference ⁴⁶).

Indeed starting from

$$\left(\frac{\delta R}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})}\right)_\mu = -v(\mathbf{r}) \quad (35)$$

one has

$$\begin{aligned} t(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') &= \left(\frac{\delta^2 R}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu = \\ &= -\left(\frac{\delta v(\mathbf{r})}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu = -\left(\frac{\delta}{\delta\rho} \left(\mu - \frac{\delta F}{\delta\rho}\right)\right)_\mu = \end{aligned}$$

$$\left(\frac{\delta^2 F}{\delta\rho\delta\rho'}\right)_\mu = \frac{\delta^2 F}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')} = \eta(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \quad (36)$$

2.3 The analogy with thermodynamic functions

As stated above, when looking at the second order derivatives of the four functionals with respect to the global variables N and μ , only the derivatives of E and Ω have any significance. $(\partial^2 F/\partial^2 N)_\rho$ has no significance, since the number of electrons can not change when keeping the density fixed, as is also the reason why $(\partial^2 R/\partial^2 \mu)_\rho = -(\partial N/\partial \mu)_\rho = 0$ (see also ⁴⁶). The global hardness $(\partial^2 E/\partial^2 N)_v = \eta$ is always positive, while $(\partial^2 \Omega/\partial^2 \mu)_v$, equaling minus the global softness is always negative. As discussed above, both the derivatives with respect to $v(\mathbf{r})$ are negative semidefinite (with $(\delta^2 \Omega/\delta v(\mathbf{r})\delta v(\mathbf{r}'))_\mu = -s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ and the softness kernel thus being positive definite) and the hardness kernel corresponding to both the second functional derivative with respect to ρ of F (without constraint) and R (with μ -constraint) is positive semi definite. Summarizing, second order (functional) derivatives with respect to extensive variables (N and ρ) are positive or positive semi definite, while derivatives with respect to intensive variables (μ and v) are negative or negative semi definite. This behavior of DFT functionals completely parallels the second derivative behavior of the functions in macroscopic thermodynamics ⁵⁶ as summarized in Table 1, where the sign alternation when passing from extensive to intensive quantities is clear. Thermodynamical potentials and DFT functionals are convex in extensive variables and concave in intensive variables.

In macroscopic thermodynamics second derivatives of state functions play an important role in stability analysis (see e.g. ⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ for an extensive treatment). Take for example the entropy, S written as $S = S(U, V)$ where the number of particles is kept constant, the quantity for which the basic extremum principle of thermodynamics can be formulated,

Table 1 Analogy between the sign of the second order derivatives of the thermodynamic functions and those of the DFT functionals (positive or negative semidefiniteness in the case of functional derivatives).

	S	V	T	P	N	ρ	μ	v
U	+	+			F	/	+	
F		+	-		R		+	0
H	+			-	E	+		-
G			-	-	Ω		-	-
		extensive	intensive			extensive	intensive	

The sequence of DFT functionals (deviating from the one in equations (1) through (4)) is chosen so as to have a maximum analogy with the thermodynamic potentials in (number of) intensive and extensive variables. A zero value or absence of a sign (/) are discussed in the text. Extensive and intensive character of the variables is indicated. For both panels the two couples of conjugated variables are (1,3) and (2,4) respectively. The structure of the DFT part of the Table highlights again (cf. Section 2.2) that only four kernels are at stake in the discussion, two with an extensive variable (ρ) (F and R) and two with an intensive variable (v) (E and Ω).

namely that for $S = S(U, V)$ $dS = 0$ and $d^2S \leq 0$ at equilibrium. The stability condition can then be written as⁵⁶

$$S_{UU}(\Delta U)^2 + 2S_{UV}(\Delta U)(\Delta V) + S_{VV}(\Delta V)^2 \leq 0 \quad (37)$$

with obvious notations for the second order derivatives S_{UU} , S_{UV} and S_{VV} . Multiplying by S_{UU} (which is negative in view of the maximum entropy postulate) and adding and subtracting $S_{UV}^2(\Delta V)^2$, one obtains

$$S_{UU}^2(\Delta U)^2 + 2S_{UV}S_{UU}(\Delta U)(\Delta V) + S_{UV}S_{VV}(\Delta V)^2 + S_{UV}^2S_{UU}(\Delta V)^2 - S_{UV}^2S_{UU}(\Delta V)^2 \geq 0 \quad (38)$$

which, after rearrangement of the terms, becomes,

$$(S_{UU}(\Delta U) + S_{UV}(\Delta V))^2 + (S_{UV}S_{VV} - S_{UV}^2)(\Delta V)^2 \geq 0 \quad (39)$$

leading to the condition that

$$(S_{UV}S_{VV} - S_{UV}^2) \geq 0 \quad (40)$$

Together with the fact that S_{UU} and S_{VV} are negative⁵⁶, this condition of stability expresses the concavity of $S(U, V)$ in all directions. This third condition yields additional conditions for physical quantities that should be obeyed^{57,58}, on top of those for S_{UU} and S_{VV}

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial U^2}\right)_v = -\frac{1}{NT^2C_v} \leq 0 \quad (41)$$

expressing that the molecular heat capacity C_v should be positive in a stable system. The stability conditions are thus identical to the conditions of convexity/concavity and as the latter have been formulated above for the DFT functionals in the different ensembles, it is tempting to see how these conditions, supplemented with the third condition equivalent to asking concavity/convexity in all directions, could be extended to DFT and which conditions can be derived from it at the electronic structure level, taking again into account the division of variables into intensive and extensive ones as in thermodynamics.

The analogy to $S(U, V)$ is, however, difficult to draw, as no DFT functional is depending on two extensive variables. Taking the opposite situation of a thermodynamic function and DFT functional depending on two intensive variables, the analogy between $G(T, p)$ and $\Omega[\mu, v(\mathbf{r})]$ can be drawn.

G is concave in p and T (this can be traced back to the maximum entropy postulate, its equivalence to the minimum energy (U) principle, and the properties of the Legendre transformations of transforming U into G). The Legendre transformations replace the two extensive variables S and V by their conjugates T and p , turning the convex behavior into a concave one. Concavity along all directions implies

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial p^2}\right)_T = \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial p}\right)_T \leq 0 \quad \text{or} \quad -\kappa_T V \leq 0, \quad (42)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial T^2}\right)_p = -\left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial T}\right)_p \leq 0 \quad \text{or} \quad -\frac{C_p}{T} \leq 0 \quad (43)$$

and

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial p^2}\right)_T \left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial T^2}\right)_p - \left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial p \partial T}\right) \geq 0 \quad (44)$$

The first two conditions express that the isothermal compressibility $\kappa_T = -\frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial p}\right)_T$ and the heat capacity at constant pressure C_p should be positive.

The third condition yields the inequality

$$\frac{\kappa_T}{V} \geq \frac{1}{C_p} \alpha^2 T \quad (45)$$

as $\left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial p \partial T}\right) = \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T}\right)_p = \alpha V$, where α is the coefficient of thermal expansion $\frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T}\right)_p$.

This is the same inequality derived by Rice, Ross and Berry for the $U(S, V)$ stability⁵⁸.

Let us now look at the analogy of $G(T, p)$ with $\Omega[\mu, v(\mathbf{r})]$, which is known to yield $\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2}\right)_v = -S$ ³, or minus the global softness, which is always negative, showing the concavity of Ω in μ . As shown above Ω is also concave in $v(\mathbf{r})$ with associated the positive semi definite softness kernel ($s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = -\left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}) \delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu$). The third condition imposing concavity in all directions can be derived from the second (functional) differential as follows.

The condition for concavity in all directions for Ω can be written as follows, extending Callen's⁵⁶ approach for the $S(U, V)$ function to the Ω functional, leading to single or double functional derivatives instead of partial derivatives.

$$d\Omega^{(2)} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2}\right)_v \Delta \mu^2 + 2 \int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r})}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \Delta \mu + \iint \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}) \delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \leq 0 \quad (46)$$

By multiplying with $\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2}\right)_v$, which is negative (as it is minus the softness, $-S$) and adding and subtracting $\int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r})}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}'$ the following inequality arises:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2}\right)_v^2 \Delta \mu^2 + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2}\right)_v \int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r})}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \Delta \mu + \\ & \int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r})}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' + \\ & \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2}\right)_v \iint \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}) \delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' - \\ & \int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r})}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Collecting the first three terms and the last two, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2}\right)_v \Delta \mu + \int \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r})}\right) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}\right]^2 + \\ & \iint \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2}\right)_v \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}) \delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)_\mu - \right. \\ & \left. \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r})}\right) \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r}')}\right)\right] \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

As the first term is larger than or equal to zero, the condition on the second term to be larger than or equal to zero, for arbitrary

$\Delta\mu$ and $\Delta v(\mathbf{r})$ becomes

$$\iint \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial \mu^2} \right)_v \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}) \delta v(\mathbf{r}')} \right)_\mu - \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r})} \right) \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Omega}{\delta \mu \delta v(\mathbf{r}')} \right) \right] \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \geq 0 \quad (49)$$

which, by filling in the definitions of the global softness S , local softness $s(\mathbf{r})$ and softness kernel $s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ becomes

$$\iint [S \cdot s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') - s(\mathbf{r})s(\mathbf{r}')] \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \geq 0 \quad (50)$$

which is the extra condition for concavity of Ω in all directions combining global and local softness and the softness kernel in a single inequality.

Taking the particular choice of a dirac delta function, $\Delta v(\mathbf{r}) = \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1)$ and $\Delta v(\mathbf{r}') = \delta(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}_1)$, as $\Delta v(\mathbf{r})$ is arbitrary, one obtains

$$S \cdot s(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_1) - s(\mathbf{r}_1)s(\mathbf{r}_1) \geq 0 \quad (51)$$

or

$$s(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_1) \geq \frac{s(\mathbf{r}_1)^2}{S} \geq 0 \quad (52)$$

This inequality shows that the third condition implies that all diagonal elements of the softness kernel should be positive, as opposed to the linear response function, where they are negative^{20,21}. Remark that this type of inequality is also unique as in only one of the four different representations the third condition is at stake and that on top of that the passage from non-local to local and global quantity corresponds in this case to simple integration which is not the case in the other representations. The formal analogy with the $F = F(N, \rho)$ case is left out of consideration in view of the above discussed peculiarities with the ρ dependence of N .

Eq. (52) puts a restriction on the relative values of the softness descriptors S , $s(\mathbf{r})$ and $s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ and is an analogue to the thermodynamic expression involving κ , α and C_p . This result is compatible with the famous Berkowitz-Parr formula²⁴, relating the ρ versus v functional derivative for two different constraints (constant N , leading to χ and constant μ , leading to the softness kernel)

$$s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = -\chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') + \frac{s(\mathbf{r})s(\mathbf{r}')}{S} \quad (53)$$

and our finding that $\chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}) \leq 0$ ²¹, converting (53) in the $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}'$ case to an inequality

$$-\chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}) = s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}) - \frac{s(\mathbf{r})^2}{S} \geq 0, \quad (54)$$

retrieving our conclusions above.

Two of the other DFT functionals, $E = E[N, v]$ and $R = R[\mu, \rho]$ combine an extensive and an intensive variable and thus have both a positive and a negative second order (functional) derivative (Table 1) but no third condition for concavity and convexity in all directions: For E the well-known result for the convexity of $E(N)$ yields a positive hardness

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_v = \eta \geq 0 \quad (55)$$

whereas the linear response function is negative semidefinite as already mentioned above

$$\iint \left(\frac{\delta^2 E}{\delta v(\mathbf{r}) \delta v(\mathbf{r}')} \right)_N \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' = \iint \chi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \Delta v(\mathbf{r}) \Delta v(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \leq 0 \quad (56)$$

For R , one gets

$$\iint \left(\frac{\delta^2 R}{\delta \rho(\mathbf{r}) \delta \rho(\mathbf{r}')} \right)_N \Delta \rho(\mathbf{r}) \Delta \rho(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' = \iint t(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \Delta \rho(\mathbf{r}) \Delta \rho(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \geq 0 \quad (57)$$

The condition on R with respect to μ has no physical meaning, since it would require a change in the number of electrons N at constant density ρ , which is obviously impossible:

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 R}{\partial \mu^2} \right)_\rho = -\frac{1}{\left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_\rho} \quad (58)$$

Due to the mixed behaviour of these functionals, depending on both an extensive and an intensive variable, this situation is analogues to the thermodynamic potentials H and F . The fourth DFT functional $F = F[\rho]$ can not be considered in a similar way since it is only dependent on one variable, ρ . It should be noticed that in this paper zero temperature DFT was at stake. It would be nice in the future to explore the analogies between the more realistic finite temperature dependent DFT, which recently gained much interest also in the context of conceptual DFT (see for example references^{61,62}), and its thermodynamic counterparts.

Finally note that in thermodynamics a second Legendre transform series of quantities was defined, now starting from the entropy, leading to four entropy dimensioned thermodynamic functions: the Massieu function(s) useful in the theory of irreversible thermodynamics and statistical thermodynamics⁵⁶. It would be tempting to see, if starting from the convexity/concavity properties of these functions and an appropriately defined DFT analogue of the entropy, supplementary conditions on the electronic structure properties of atomic or molecular systems could be derived.

3 Conclusions

In this study the convexity/concavity of the functionals E , Ω , F and R of the four different ensemble representations used in (conceptual) density functional theory is scrutinized and connected with the positive/negative semidefiniteness of the associated kernels. A comparison with the four energy dimensioned thermodynamical state-functions U , F , H , G , just as the DFT functionals interrelated by Legendre transformations, along the lines set out by Nalewajski and Parr shows that stability conditions in Thermodynamics are similar in structure to convexity/concavity conditions for DFT functionals. In the case of functionals which are twice convex or twice concave in their variables, the condition for concavity/convexity in all directions yields a inequality involving the

three second order (functional) derivatives of the functional considered. In case of Ω (the only functional obeying both the aforementioned conditions and the condition of non-interdependency of its variables), an inequality involving global softness, local softness and the softness kernel then results, which is shown to be compatible with the Berkowitz-Parr relationship. It might be tempting to extend this study to finite temperature DFT and to see if analogous relationships might be put forward for DFT functionals which are the analogues of the entropy dimensioned thermodynamic functions as the Massieu function, demanding an entropy analogue in DFT.

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